

$P = NP$

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Abstract. P versus NP is considered as one of the great open problems of science. This consists in knowing the answer of the following question: Is P equal to NP ? This problem was first mentioned in a letter written by John Nash to the National Security Agency in 1955. However, a precise statement of the P versus NP problem was introduced independently by Stephen Cook and Leonid Levin. Since that date, all efforts to find a proof for this huge problem have failed. If any single NP -complete problem can be solved in polynomial time, then every NP problem has a polynomial time algorithm. $BETWEENNESS$ is a well-known NP -complete problem. We prove there is a polynomial time algorithm which decides $BETWEENNESS$. In this way, we demonstrate the complexity class P is equal to NP .

Keywords: $P \cdot NP \cdot NP$ -complete $\cdot BETWEENNESS \cdot 2SAT$.

1 Introduction

The P versus NP problem is a major unsolved problem in computer science [4]. This is considered by many to be the most important open problem in the field [4]. It is one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems selected by the Clay Mathematics Institute to carry a US\$1,000,000 prize for the first correct solution [4]. It was essentially mentioned in 1955 from a letter written by John Nash to the United States National Security Agency [1]. However, the precise statement of the $P = NP$ problem was introduced in 1971 by Stephen Cook in a seminal paper [4].

In 1936, Turing developed his theoretical computational model [14]. The deterministic and nondeterministic Turing machines have become in two of the most important definitions related to this theoretical model for computation [14]. A deterministic Turing machine has only one next action for each step defined in its program or transition function [14]. A nondeterministic Turing machine could contain more than one action defined for each step of its program, where this one is no longer a function, but a relation [14].

Another relevant advance in the last century has been the definition of a complexity class. A language over an alphabet is any set of strings made up of symbols from that alphabet [5]. A complexity class is a set of problems, which

are represented as a language, grouped by measures such as the running time, memory, etc [5].

In the computational complexity theory, the class P contains those languages that can be decided in polynomial time by a deterministic Turing machine [10]. The class NP consists in those languages that can be decided in polynomial time by a nondeterministic Turing machine [10]. The biggest open question in theoretical computer science concerns the relationship between these classes: Is P equal to NP ? In 2012, a poll of 151 researchers showed that 126 (83%) believed the answer to be no, 12 (9%) believed the answer is yes, 5 (3%) believed the question may be independent of the currently accepted axioms and therefore impossible to prove or disprove, 8 (5%) said either do not know or do not care or don't want the answer to be yes nor the problem to be resolved [9].

P versus NP is one of the greatest open problems in science and a correct solution for this incognita will have a great impact not only for computer science, but for many other fields as well [1]. Whether $P = NP$ or not is still a controversial and unsolved problem [1]. In this work, we proved the complexity class P is equal to NP . Hence, we solved one of the most important open problems in computer science. Besides, we provide a computational polynomial time solution programmed in Scala [15].

2 Results

Definition 1. *BETWEENNESS*

INSTANCE: A positive integer n and a collection C of ordered triples (a, b, c) of distinct elements from a set $\{1, \dots, n\}$. Every element in the set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ is in at least one triple of C .

QUESTION: Is there a one-to-one function $f : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that for each $(a, b, c) \in C$, we have either $f(a) < f(b) < f(c)$ or $f(a) > f(b) > f(c)$?

*REMARKS: *BETWEENNESS* $\in NP$ -complete [8].*

Theorem 1. **BETWEENNESS* $\in P$.*

Proof. The polynomial time solution is described in the pseudo code Algorithm 1.

If there is a one-to-one function $f : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$, then we define x_{ij} is true if and only if the possible function f complies with $f(i) - f(j) > 0$. In the first step we add to the Boolean formula F the clauses $(x_{ij} \vee x_{ji}) \wedge (\neg x_{ij} \vee \neg x_{ji})$ for every pair $i \neq j$ of elements in $\{1, \dots, n\}$, because only one of the literals x_{ij}, x_{ji} is true since is true either $f(i) - f(j) > 0$ or $f(j) - f(i) > 0$. In the second step for each triple $(a, b, c) \in C$ we add the clauses $(x_{ab} \vee x_{cb}) \wedge (\neg x_{ab} \vee \neg x_{cb})$, because if $f(a) < f(b) < f(c)$ or $f(a) > f(b) > f(c)$ then $f(a) - f(b) < 0 < f(c) - f(b)$ or $f(a) - f(b) > 0 > f(c) - f(b)$ so only one of the literals x_{ab}, x_{cb} is true since is true either $f(a) - f(b) > 0$ or $f(c) - f(b) > 0$. In the third step for each triple $(a, b, c) \in C$ we add the clauses $(\neg x_{ba} \vee x_{ca}) \wedge (x_{ba} \vee \neg x_{ca})$, because if $f(a) < f(b) < f(c)$ or $f(a) > f(b) > f(c)$ then $0 < f(b) - f(a) < f(c) - f(a)$ or

Algorithm 1 Polynomial time algorithm from *BETWEENNESS*

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1: /*A collection  $C$  of ordered triples of distinct elements from a set  $\{1, \dots, n\}$ */
2: procedure ALGO( $n, C$ )
3:   /*Create the empty formula*/
4:    $F \leftarrow \{\}$ 
5:   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
6:     for  $j \leftarrow i + 1$  to  $n$  do
7:        $F \leftarrow F \wedge (x_{ij} \vee x_{ji}) \wedge (\neg x_{ij} \vee \neg x_{ji})$ 
8:     end for
9:   end for
10:  /*For each ordered triple in  $C^*$ */
11:  for all  $(a, b, c) \in C$  do
12:     $F \leftarrow F \wedge (x_{ab} \vee x_{cb}) \wedge (\neg x_{ab} \vee \neg x_{cb})$ 
13:     $F \leftarrow F \wedge (\neg x_{ba} \vee x_{ca}) \wedge (x_{ba} \vee \neg x_{ca})$ 
14:     $F \leftarrow F \wedge (\neg x_{bc} \vee x_{ac}) \wedge (x_{bc} \vee \neg x_{ac})$ 
15:  end for
16:  return SATISFIABLE( $n, F$ )
17: end procedure

```

$0 > f(b) - f(a) > f(c) - f(a)$ so both of the literals x_{ba}, x_{ca} have the same value since is true either $f(b) - f(a) > 0$ and $f(c) - f(a) > 0$ or $f(b) - f(a) < 0$ and $f(c) - f(a) < 0$. In the fourth step for each triple $(a, b, c) \in C$ we add the clauses $(\neg x_{bc} \vee x_{ac}) \wedge (x_{bc} \vee \neg x_{ac})$, because if $f(a) < f(b) < f(c)$ or $f(a) > f(b) > f(c)$ then $f(a) - f(c) < f(b) - f(c) < 0$ or $f(a) - f(c) > f(b) - f(c) > 0$ so both of the literals x_{bc}, x_{ac} have the same value since is true either $f(b) - f(c) > 0$ and $f(a) - f(c) > 0$ or $f(b) - f(c) < 0$ and $f(a) - f(c) < 0$.

Now, note that the first step guarantee that f must be an asymmetric relation, because there is no solution on F such that $i \neq j$ and the possible function f complies with $f(i) - f(j) = 0$. Note also the other steps guarantee for each triple $(a, b, c) \in C$ we must have either $f(a) < f(b) < f(c)$ or $f(a) > f(b) > f(c)$, because there is no solution on F where $f(a) > f(b) < f(c)$ or $f(a) < f(b) > f(c)$ could be true since that possibility never satisfies the clauses from these steps. However, the above clauses do not guarantee the transitivity that should exist in the function f . For that reason, we call another Algorithm 2 to check whether there is a satisfying truth assignment of F which satisfies at the same time the transitivity of the function f .

Since this truth assignment must always be a satisfying truth assignment, then we follow the algorithm described in [2]. First, we find the graph of the strong connected components by the Tarjan algorithm [5]. Then, we iterate for each strong connected component, check whether this contains the same positive and negated literal or try to verify whether there is no possible transitivity where the whole literals of the component are either true or false. Besides, for each strong connected component *StrongConnectedComponent* we consider the two set of literals *UnionSCC* and *NegatedUnionSCC*.

Algorithm 2 Check whether the formula is satisfiable under the transitivity

```

1: function SATISFIABLE( $n, F$ )
2:   /*Create the empty map where there will be stored the current visited components*/
3:   MapVisited  $\leftarrow$  []
4:   /*Get the strong connected components of the graph that represents the implications in  $F^*$ */
5:   ListSCC  $\leftarrow$  TarjanStrongConnectedComponents( $F$ )
6:   /*Iterate from the strong connected components*/
7:   for all StrongConnectedComponent  $\in$  ListSCC do
8:     /*When the Boolean formula  $F$  is not satisfiable*/
9:     if StrongConnectedComponent contains a literal and its negation then
10:      return "no"
11:    end if
12:    /*We can reject when the strong connected component has no transitivity*/
13:    if NOTTRANSITIVITY( $n, \text{StrongConnectedComponent}$ ) = true then
14:      return "no"
15:    end if
16:    if MapVisited[StrongConnectedComponent] = false then
17:      ArrayPair  $\leftarrow$  SETTRANSITIVITY(StrongConnectedComponent, ListSCC, MapVisited)
18:      UnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  ArrayPair[1]
19:      NegatedUnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  ArrayPair[2]
20:      /*We can reject when these both strong connected components have no transitivity*/
21:      if NOTTRANSITIVITY( $n, \text{UnionSCC}$ ) = true  $\wedge$ 
NOTTRANSITIVITY( $n, \text{NegatedUnionSCC}$ ) = true then
22:        return "no"
23:      end if
24:    end if
25:  end for
26:  return "yes"
27: end function

```

Algorithm 3 SETTRANSITIVITY of a current strong connected component

```

1: function SETTRANSITIVITY(StrongConnectedComponent, ListSCC, MapVisited)
2:   /*Create a set of a union of strong connected components as empty*/
3:   UnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  {}
4:   /*Create another set of a union of strong connected components as empty*/
5:   NegatedUnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  {}
6:   /*Create an empty data structure queue*/
7:   Queue  $\leftarrow$  {}
8:   /*Add the pair of the current component and the index 0*/
9:   Queue.Add((StrongConnectedComponent, 0))
10:  MapVisited[StrongConnectedComponent]  $\leftarrow$  true
11:  while Queue.size > 0 do
12:    /*Extract and remove the first element in the Queue*/
13:    (SCC, j)  $\leftarrow$  Queue.Poll()
14:    /*Iterate from the strong connected components*/
15:    for all AnotherSCC  $\in$  ListSCC do
16:      /*When AnotherSCC has not been marked as visited*/
17:      if MapVisited[AnotherSCC] = false then
18:        /*When AnotherSCC contains a literal that is negated in SCC*/
19:        if AnotherSCC contains a literal negated in SCC then
20:          if j = 0 then
21:            /*Add the elements to the set UnionSCC*/
22:            UnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  UnionSCC  $\cup$  AnotherSCC
23:            /*Add the elements to the set NegatedUnionSCC converting
the positive literals to negated literals and viceversa from AnotherSCC*/
24:            NegatedUnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  NegatedUnionSCC  $\cup$ 
Negate(AnotherSCC)
25:          else
26:            /*Interchange the negations of literals for the sets UnionSCC
and NegatedUnionSCC*/
27:            UnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  UnionSCC  $\cup$  Negate(AnotherSCC)
28:            NegatedUnionSCC  $\leftarrow$  NegatedUnionSCC  $\cup$  AnotherSCC
29:          end if
30:          /*Enqueue another pair with the current iterated component and
the new index 1 when j = 0 otherwise the index is 0*/
31:          Queue.Add((AnotherSCC, (j + 1) remainder with 2))
32:          /*Mark as visited the selected component AnotherSCC*/
33:          MapVisited[AnotherSCC]  $\leftarrow$  true
34:        end if
35:      end if
36:    end for
37:  end while
38:  /*Return one array with the sets result*/
39:  return [UnionSCC, NegatedUnionSCC]
40: end function

```

Algorithm 4 NOTTRANSITIVITY in a strong connected component

```

1: function NOTTRANSITIVITY( $n, Set$ )
2:   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
3:     for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
4:       if  $i \neq j$  then
5:         for  $k \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
6:           if  $i \neq k \wedge k \neq j$  then
7:             /*When the set does not comply with the transitivity*/
8:             if  $\{x_{ij}, x_{jk}, x_{ki}\} \subseteq Set$  then
9:               return true
10:            end if
11:            if  $\{\neg x_{ij}, \neg x_{jk}, \neg x_{ki}\} \subseteq Set$  then
12:              return true
13:            end if
14:            if  $\{x_{ji}, x_{kj}, x_{ik}\} \subseteq Set$  then
15:              return true
16:            end if
17:            if  $\{\neg x_{ji}, \neg x_{kj}, \neg x_{ik}\} \subseteq Set$  then
18:              return true
19:            end if
20:          end if
21:        end for
22:      end if
23:    end for
24:  end for
25:  return false
26: end function

```

On the one hand, if all the literals in the strong connected component *StrongConnectedComponent* are false, then all the literals in *UnionSCC* should be true. Therefore, we must check that the set *UnionSCC* complies with the transitivity of the function f . The reasons are obvious: The first sets which contain *UnionSCC* in the first iteration of the Algorithm 3 are those which contain a literal negated in the current component *StrongConnectedComponent*. In the second iterations of each enqueue component of the first iteration, we would have in *UnionSCC* the negation of the literals which are contained in the strong connected components that contain a literal negated from the elements in the first iteration. Since the sets of the first iteration in the construction of *UnionSCC* should be true, then the other ones should be false, and thus its negation of the inner literals should be true. As result, we continue with this iteration interchanging between the negation or not of the literals inside of the strong connected components in the list.

On the other hand, if all the literals in the strong connected component *StrongConnectedComponent* are true, then all the literals in the another set *NegatedUnionSCC* should be true. Hence, we must check that the another set *NegatedUnionSCC* complies with the transitivity of the function f as well. The first sets which contain *NegatedUnionSCC* in the first iteration of the Algorithm 3 are those which contain a literal negated in the current component *StrongConnectedComponent*, but this time with the negation of the literals which these ones could contain. The reason is because these strong connected components should be false when the literals in the *StrongConnectedComponent* are true, therefore the negation of the literals should be evaluated as true. In the second iterations of each enqueue component of the first iteration, we would have in *NegatedUnionSCC* the literals, but this time without making a negation of each one, which are contained in the strong connected components that contain a literal negated from the elements in the first iteration. Since the sets of the first iteration in the construction of *NegatedUnionSCC* should be false, then the next ones should be true, and thus there is no necessity of making a negation of these literals. As result, we continue with this iteration interchanging between the negation or not of the literals inside of the strong connected components in the list.

Since every strong connected component *StrongConnectedComponent* must be either true or false for any truth assignment of the Boolean formula F , then at least one of the set *UnionSCC* or *NegatedUnionSCC* must comply with the transitivity of the function f . Consequently, we can reject when both sets do not comply with the transitivity property. In addition, we use a map of visited strong connected components *MapVisited*, so we do not have to make the same verification twice and gain in efficiency.

A set of literals from the strong connected components does not satisfies the transitivity of the function f if this one contains the set of literals $\{x_{ij}, x_{jk}, x_{ki}\}$. The reason is obvious: If all the literals are true, then $f(i) > f(j)$, $f(j) > f(k)$ and $f(k) > f(i)$, but this is no possible due to the rules of the transitivity relation since if $f(i) > f(j)$ and $f(j) > f(k)$ is true, therefore necessarily $f(i) > f(k)$ is

true. The same happens when the set of literals $\{x_{ij}, x_{jk}, x_{ki}\}$ are false. In that case, we obtain $f(i) < f(j)$, $f(j) < f(k)$ and $f(k) < f(i)$, but this is also not possible since if $f(i) < f(j)$ and $f(j) < f(k)$, therefore necessarily $f(i) < f(k)$ is true. Something similar we deduce from the sets of literals $\{\neg x_{ij}, \neg x_{jk}, \neg x_{ki}\}$ or $\{x_{ji}, x_{kj}, x_{ik}\}$ since when they are all true then the literals $\{x_{ij}, x_{jk}, x_{ki}\}$ are all false and viceversa, therefore they are equivalent. We can apply the same arguments in $\{\neg x_{ji}, \neg x_{kj}, \neg x_{ik}\}$.

Finally, if we have success with these steps, then there is a satisfying truth assignment which complies with the properties of transitivity from the possible function f and thus the instance belongs to BETWEENNESS. The four Algorithms 1, 2, 3 and 4 are computed in polynomial time. Consequently, we can affirm that $BETWEENNESS \in P$ and the proof is completed.

Theorem 2. $P = NP$.

Proof. If any single NP -complete problem can be solved in polynomial time, then every NP problem has a polynomial time algorithm [5]. $BETWEENNESS$ can be solved in polynomial time. Since $BETWEENNESS$ is a well-known NP -complete problem [8], then $P = NP$.

3 Conclusions

No one has been able to find a polynomial time algorithm for any of more than 300 important known NP -complete problems [8]. A proof of $P = NP$ will have stunning practical consequences, because it leads to efficient methods for solving some of the important problems in NP [4]. The consequences, both positive and negative, arise since various NP -complete problems are fundamental in many fields [4].

Cryptography, for example, relies on certain problems being difficult. A constructive and efficient solution to an NP -complete problem such as 3SAT will break most existing cryptosystems including: Public-key cryptography [11], symmetric ciphers [12] and one-way functions used in cryptographic hashing [6]. These would need to be modified or replaced by information-theoretically secure solutions not inherently based on P - NP equivalence.

There are enormous positive consequences that will follow from rendering tractable many currently mathematically intractable problems. For instance, many problems in operations research are NP -complete, such as some types of integer programming and the traveling salesman problem [8]. Efficient solutions to these problems have enormous implications for logistics [4]. Many other important problems, such as some problems in protein structure prediction, are also NP -complete, so this will spur considerable advances in biology [3]. Furthermore, this could be a huge advance in medicine, since the cancer might be cured by this solution [7].

But such changes may pale in significance compared to the revolution an efficient method for solving NP -complete problems will cause in mathematics itself [1]. Research mathematicians spend their careers trying to prove theorems,

and some proofs have taken decades or even centuries to find after problems have been stated [1]. For instance, Fermat’s Last Theorem took over three centuries to prove. A method that is guaranteed to find proofs to theorems, should one exist of a “reasonable” size, would essentially end this struggle [1].

Indeed, this proof of $P = NP$ could solve not merely one Millennium Problem but all seven of them [1]. This observation is based on once we fix a formal system such as the first-order logic plus the axioms of ZF set theory, then we can find a demonstration in time polynomial in n when a given statement has a proof with at most n symbols long in that system [1]. This is assuming that the other six Clay conjectures have ZF proofs that are not too large such as it was the Perelman’s case [13].

Besides, a $P = NP$ proof reveals the existence of an interesting relationship between humans and machines [1]. For example, suppose we want to program a computer to create new Mozart-quality symphonies and Shakespeare-quality plays. When $P = NP$, this could be reduced to the easier problem of writing a computer program to recognize great works of art [1].

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